

Editorial

***Energies* Best Paper Award 2014**

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Last year, *Energies* (ISSN 1996-1073) decided to award a prize to outstanding papers in the area of energy technologies and applications published in *Energies*. In 2014, the Prize Awarding Committee has decided to also grant awards in the category of “best review papers”.

We are now pleased to announce the “*Energies* Best Review Papers Award” for 2014. Nominations were made by the Editor-in-Chief and by the Editorial Board members from among all review papers published in 2010. The awards went to:

1st Prize

Manfred Lenzen

Current State of Development of Electricity-Generating Technologies: A Literature Review

Energies **2010**, *3*(3), 462-591; doi: 10.3390/en3030462

Available online: <http://www.mdpi.com/1996-1073/3/3/462>

2nd Prize

Vladimir Alvarado and Eduardo Manrique

Enhanced Oil Recovery: An Update Review

Energies **2010**, *3*(9), 1529-1575; doi: 10.3390/en3091529

Available online: <http://www.mdpi.com/1996-1073/3/9/1529>

3rd Prize

Melanie Kuhn and Teko W. Napporn

Single-Chamber Solid Oxide Fuel Cell Technology—From Its Origins to Today’s State of the Art

Energies **2010**, *3*(1), 57-134; doi: 10.3390/en3010057

Available online: <http://www.mdpi.com/1996-1073/3/1/57>

We believe that these three truly outstanding papers are valuable contributions to *Energies* and to the scientific community. On behalf of the Prize Awarding Committee of *Energies*, we would like to congratulate these three teams for their excellent work. In recognition of their accomplishment, all the authors of the three papers, Dr. Manfred Lenzen, Dr. Vladimir Alvarado, Dr. Eduardo Manrique, Dr. Melanie Kuhn and Dr. Teko W. Napporn will be each offered the privilege of publishing a paper free of charge in open access format in *Energies*, after the usual peer-review procedure.

The Prize Awarding Committee

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